

Type II Diabetes

Introduction

Diabetes is usually caused by the problems in the way an individual's body makes to uses up insulin. Insulin is required to move the blood sugar glucose into cells, where it is stored for the later uses as energy. During the types II diabetes, the fats, liver and muscles cells do not respond properly to the insulin. This is known as insulin resistance. As a result, the blood sugar does not get into the cells to be stored for energy. It is unavoidable and preventable through exercises and diet.

Discussion

Type II Diabetes

Diabetes mellitus type II is a chronic metabolic disease, which leads to elevated blood glucose levels. The increased blood glucose levels damage blood vessels and nerves in the long run and can lead to numerous organ problems. The sequels of diabetes include heart attack, stroke, kidney failure, retinal damage, erectile dysfunction and many others. The term "late effects" is misleading because many diabetes-related illnesses can occur already in the early stages of diabetes; this is often only a prediabetes is diabetes preliminary). In the past, the type II diabetes was also sometimes called the "Age of sugar." In fact, at the first place, the elderly people fall victim to it (Risérus, Willett, Hu, 2009). However, because more and more people are severely overweight at a young age and move very little, the young people fall increasingly ill and those at 30 - to 40-year-old with type II diabetes. This disease is increasingly being found also in children and adolescents.

Diabetes Mellitus is one of the oldest known diseases, which is already described in an Egyptian papyrus. In the United States and other various regions, about 90 percent people of the people suffering from diabetes have type II diabetes.

Causes

The Type II diabetes is a disease in which the first cause is the lack of insulin in the foreground. Rather, it is due to an inherited predisposition, promoted by obesity and lack of exercise, which results into insulin resistance. This means that the cells are resistant (resistant) to insulin and the hormone so that the sugar cannot infiltrate. Therefore, there is an increase in blood sugar levels. In order to overcome the insulin resistance, the pancreas produces more insulin initially. Over the years, however, they can produce more insulin to "exhaust" the insulin-

producing beta cells in the pancreas and increases the blood sugar level (Malik; Popkin, Bray, Willett, Hu, 2010).

The predisposition to developing diabetes mellitus type II is hereditary. If close relatives (especially parents, siblings) have Type II diabetes, the probability of developing cancer later in life as well, goes up to 60 percent. The other causes of the emergence of type II diabetes are the obesity and lack of exercise. Both provide an insulin resistance feed, which is one of the main causes of type II diabetes. Insulin resistance means that the cells of the body insensitive to insulin. The pancreatic hormone can no longer properly infiltrate the sugar from the blood into the cells where it is used for energy or stored in some cases. Fat, especially belly fat tissue pours chemical messengers that promote insulin resistance and this may also be due to the lack of exercise in particular the encourages the muscle insulin resistance. First, the body tries to overcome the insulin resistance by distributing more insulin (American Diabetes Association, 2010). In the early stages of diabetes, the insulin level in the blood is therefore increased, and finally, the insulin production is exhausted. The insulin level drops and the blood sugar level rises until it is so high that the criteria for the diagnosis of diabetes mellitus have been met. The Metabolic Syndrome, poor nutrition and lack of exercise are among the main causes of type II diabetes. Diabetes mellitus type II occurs frequently in the "package" with increased blood pressure (up to 80 percent of type II diabetes develop over time, high blood pressure) to obesity and dyslipidemia.

Treatment

The Type-II diabetes, in contrast to type-1 diabetes, is usually treated initially by a change in lifestyle, which has a beneficial effect on insulin resistance. There are tablets that help

to improve the action of insulin or stimulate the release of insulin. Over time, however, the patients also have to inject a lot of type-II diabetic's insulin. In addition to type-1 and type-II diabetes, there are a number of other, less common forms of diabetes (Vijan, 2010). The physicians speak in this case of the metabolic syndrome. Among other favorable genetic factors, there are mediators from adipose tissue which result in the common occurrence of the disease. In addition, the individual diseases are mutually reinforcing. There is evidence that elevated blood pressure promotes insulin resistance. Type II diabetes accounts for a long time with no complaints. Therefore, it often remains undetected for many years. Not infrequently, the disease is not diagnosed until it has already caused sequel, such as a heart attack or stroke. When blood sugar levels rise, the body tries to remove excess sugar in the urine (Ripsin, Kang, Urban, 2009).

Conclusion

Diabetes mellitus type II is by far the most common form of diabetes and concerns 90% of cases, most of which exist in the older age. It is characterized by a twofold drawback: deficiency of insulin secretion, or the insulin resistance. The result, in both cases, is the resulting increase in the level of glucose in the blood (hyperglycemia). This type of diabetes is said non-insulin-dependent because the injection of insulin outside, unlike the type 1 diabetes, is not of vital importance. The underlying causes of disease onset are generally sought in hereditary and environmental factors. Through extensive studies it was shown that there is a factor of hereditary transmission, not yet elucidated, which exhibits some populations or even in some families the disease.

References

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